

FARCLIMATE

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List of acronyms

GTA: Gender Transformative Approach

D: Deliverable

EC: European Commission

EEA: European Environment Agency

EU: European Union

IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

KoM: Kick-off Meeting

LAG: Local Action Group

LL: Living Lab

MIP4Adapt: EU Mission Implementation Platform

NGO: Non-Governmental Organisation

PU: Public

R&D: Research and Development

T: Task

SME: Small and Medium Enterprise

UN: United Nations

UNFCCC: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

WEF: World Economic Forum

WP: Work Package

Project information

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Partner No.	Organisation Name Acronym
1 (Coord.)	UNIVERSIDAD DE VIGO UVIGO
2	CONTACTICA S.L. CTA
3	INTERNATIONAL UNION FOR CONSERVATION OF NATURE UICN
4	C4G - CONSULTING AND TRAINING NETWORK, LDA C4G
5	INVIABLE LIFE CYCLE THINKING S.L. INV
6	MUNICIPIO DO FUNDAO FUNDAO
7	GREEN GROWTH GENERATION GGG
8	UNIVERSITY OF LIEGE ULIEGE
9	FUNDACIÓN CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCIÓN FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEÓN CESEFOR
10	UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA UNL
11	FUNDACIÓN PARA LA PESCA Y MARISQUEO FUNDAMAR FUNDAMAR
12	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW ENOLL
13	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS CERTH
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Abstract:	<p>This document outlines the development of the user research and content strategy for the Transformation Hub under Task T7.1 of the project, addressing the needs of the primary target audience identified in WP2. While there is substantial information on climate resilience initiatives and solutions, much of it has focused on governmental decision-makers and their supporting organisations, leaving other key stakeholders -who are crucial in driving the transition to climate resilience- underrepresented. These stakeholders play a vital role in creating and implementing effective solutions at local and regional levels. This document details the approach used and the results obtained to address this gap, from defining user archetypes within the target audience to analysing how they interact with and experience key adaptation platforms and assessing their perceptions of the relevance and decision-making value of the case study content. These insights are then incorporated into the platform's content strategy, which is presented as part of this report.</p>

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1. Executive Summary

The present document, developed in Task T7.1 as part of **WP7-- Transformative solutions for a positive climate future** of the FARCLIMATE project, synthesises the process of user research and presents both experience insights and the proposed content strategy for the Transformation Hub platform. The strategy is informed by the **Methodological Approach for FARCLIMATE** (D2.1) and the **compilation of FARCLIMATE case studies** (D2.2), grounded in the **Stakeholder Management Strategy** (D2.3) and is complemented by the guidelines outlined in the **Gender Transformative Approach** (D1.5) and the **Communication and Dissemination Plan** (D8.1) of the project.

Firstly, **Section 2** introduces the **context** and **objectives** of WP7, of which the Transformation Hub constitutes the cornerstone, outlining the strategic guidelines that serve as the starting point for the Hub's approach: **communicating scientific facts** in an inspirational way and being **user-centred** and **co-created** with the target audience. The four steps in the process of creating the FARCLIMATE Transformation Hub are summarised, and finally, the purpose and objectives of Task T.7.1 User Research and Content Strategy Development, which constitutes the first step in the process, are presented.

The **methodological approach**, structured into four complementary actions, is introduced in **Section 3**, followed by a detailed description of each action in Sections 4 to 7 of this document.

The **documentary research**, conducted to identify relevant projects and platforms within the climate adaptation ecosystem, is described in **Section 4** (**Annex 1** compiles a **list of references** for the projects and platforms considered of greatest interest to FARCLIMATE). The activities that, alongside this research, enabled initial exploration with potential users are briefly presented in **Section 5**. **Section 6** then addresses the review of the original approach and the definition of the **target audience** and scale, establishing the **guidelines** that were applied for a deeper investigation into the needs and priorities of potential users through interviews.

Section 7 begins with the **approach** and **script** for **semi-structured interviews**, followed by the **qualitative analysis** of the interviews, which includes the documentation and coding of insights from individual interviews and the thematic mapping and integration of the various interviews to generate a summary covering the main insights related to the topics addressed. The **mind maps** resulting from the analysis of user interviews are synthesised in **Annex 2**.

The **main results** obtained from the interviews regarding potential primary **users' perspectives** on their understanding of the impact and urgency of climate adaptation, as well as their **knowledge** of available digital resources and their utility, are described in **Section 8**. This section structures the thematic areas of insights into two main content blocks: 1) the **concept** of climate adaptation and **practices of information search**, and 2) user awareness, utility, and exploration of **knowledge platforms**.

Finally, **Section 9** presents the proposal for the **platform content strategy** for the Transformation Hub, beginning with a description of the **strategic framework** and then specifically detailing the **key features** and **content** deemed relevant based on the user research conducted.

2. Introduction

2.1 Transformative solutions for a positive climate future

The **FARCLIMATE** project addresses the complex challenges of developing and scaling climate-resilient measures, with a focus on making them **accessible** and **understandable** to all. It also tackles the social, political, and economic **barriers** that often hinder progress. FARCLIMATE prioritises **climate adaptation** by empowering local communities, ensuring that **transitions** are both **just** and **inclusive**.

As detailed in deliverable **D2.3** Stakeholder Management Strategy, **participatory approaches** are essential for addressing wicked problems (Conklin, 2006). To fully understand the various perspectives within a given context, **diversity** among participants is crucial. This diversity goes beyond professional knowledge -multi- or interdisciplinarity alone is not sufficient. We need the voices of those who are directly affected, the “experts in experience”. These individuals, alongside certified experts and decision-makers, shape both the perception and definition of the problem. To discover and develop effective solutions for complex issues, we must incorporate both those with formal expertise and those whose knowledge stems from lived experience, emphasising the importance of involving **local communities** (Sultana et al., 2024; Cattino and Reckien, 2021). In the FARCLIMATE project, user-driven Living Labs have been chosen to generate truly just and inclusive approaches to solving a range of wicked problems related to climate change adaptation across different territories and communities. In this sense, the Living Labs in FARCLIMATE resemble Citizen Labs more than traditional R&D Labs.

In summary, addressing wicked problems requires inclusive, context-specific approaches that engage a diverse range of participants, particularly those who live and experience the issues firsthand. This approach should foster **open dialogue** between different ways of knowing, minimising pre-existing hierarchies among stakeholders. To achieve these aims, it is essential to expand and adapt our **innovation toolbox** to tackle emerging challenges. This involves engaging in immersive discovery through active participation, ensuring effective mediation to facilitate communication and collaboration among diverse stakeholders by addressing their varying needs, desires, and concerns, and fostering continuous experimentation and prototyping. These processes generate **valuable insights** for both the territory and local communities, incorporating action-based research and promoting ongoing learning.

Digital tools, platforms, content, and communities can be essential for effectively developing this kind of inclusive and participatory approach. Based on this premise, the objectives established in **WP7 - Transformative Solutions for a Positive Climate Future** are as follows:

- **07.1.** To build inspiring knowledge and meaningful experiences to accelerate climate adaptation action.
- **07.2.** To provide transformative user-centred solutions for a positive climatic future.
- **07.3.** To enhance the effectiveness of the actions and take advantage of synergies by fuelling a growing network of Connected Action for EU adaptation.

2.2 The Transformation Hub

2.2.1. Driving innovation and transforming climate adaptation narrative

The development of the Transformation Hub is the cornerstone on which WP7 pivots. This “digital artefact” - a collection of infrastructures, tools, interfaces and contents - serves as the tool through which FARCLIMATE systematises and disseminates information on climate adaptation solutions, stemming from proposals that have been conceived and developed throughout the project, as well as the extensive universe of experiences, initiatives, and prior projects in the field of climate adaptation.

Communicating scientific facts in an inspirational way

There is no doubt that **scientific understanding** of climate change has accelerated in recent decades (Rahmawaty et al., 2024), but **climate action** has not kept pace (IPCC, 2022). As the impacts of climate change become increasingly evident and public concern gains momentum, mainstreaming of adaptation in relevant policies is progressing, but at a suboptimal pace in light of the increasing frequency and intensity of the impacts. There is a clear gap between the growing body of public policies (especially at national and international levels) and the restricted number and impact of effective solutions at local and regional levels. What we’ve learned in recent decades is that knowledge does not necessarily lead to action. Research has shown that how societies respond and adapt to climate change is influenced by culture, historical memory and identity, each of which can either improve awareness and sense of urgency for specific climate-related risks, or shift attention away from others. Scientific facts are essential, but there is a clear need for the natural sciences to engage more deeply with the social sciences and humanities to consider the role of science in closing the **gap** between **knowledge and action**.

FARCLIMATE has the goal of **communicating** climate change with scientific and academic facts, but doing it in an informative and **inspirational** way, so that data and facts empower the key stakeholders. Instead of complicated data with disturbing conclusions, FARCLIMATE will follow a narrative-driven storytelling whose conclusion is that you can actually do something in the path to a climate resilient future. The outputs will include inspirational stories targeting those stakeholders who could **replicate** and **utilise** the **experiences** and **knowledge** generated and compiled in FARCLIMATE.

User-centred and co-created with the target audience

The Adaptation Knowledge Portal (AKP) was created in 2006 as a product of the Nairobi Work Programme (NWP), the UNFCCC knowledge-for-action hub for climate adaptation and resilience. Since then, **several platforms** containing **adaptation knowledge resources** (including case studies, methods and tools, publications and technical documents, etc.) have emerged, with the overall goal to provide access to information and knowledge on climate change adaptation. In the European context, Climate-ADAPT was launched in 2012 as a partnership between the European Commission (in particular DG CLIMA) and the European Environment Agency (EEA) to overcome the lack of a consistent knowledge base on adaptation in Europe. Its intended target audience includes governmental decision-makers and the organisations supporting them in the development, implementation and evaluation of climate change adaptation strategies, plans and actions at EU, transnational, national and sub-national levels. The Climate-ADAPT strategy 2022-2024 reflects the new ambition in EU adaptation

policy and includes new components such as the upgrade of the country profiles into a monitoring and reporting mechanism and the modelling information generated under the EU Destination Earth initiative. A substantial new dimension of Climate-ADAPT evolves from its new role of supporting the EU mission on adaptation to climate change, serving as the key “mission knowledge hub” to provide new services at local and regional levels to foster adaptation in those regions and communities, to increase their preparedness for the inevitable changes and extreme events, and to share experiences and solutions to prevent loss of lives and livelihoods. However, the overview of the primary Climate-ADAPT target audience (and its needs) shows a focus on a similar primary target audience, now addressing its segments more directly.

Numerous studies have identified a “usability gap” attributed to a tendency toward science-driven rather than demand-driven climate services (Brasseur and Gallardo, 2016; Lemos et al., 2012; Raaphorst et al., 2020). Collaborating with users during the design process is more challenging, but it ultimately reduces the risk of misaligned agendas between decision-makers and information providers (Daniels et al., 2020), and such **collaboration** fosters the **innovative thinking** needed to create effective climate services (Blome et al., 2017). In recent years, user evaluation has gained importance in the field of climate adaptation, with works like that of Lien et al. (2023), which focuses on the development and user evaluation of The Knowledge Bank (a web portal for national climate change adaptation data in Norway), discussing and highlighting key drivers for decision-makers and insights into the challenges and opportunities in its implementation.

Figure 1. Key steps in the creation process of the FARCLIMATE Transformation Hub

Accelerating the transformation to a climate-resilient future requires **re-contextualizing** existing **knowledge** and creating new narratives to further mobilise and inspire the engagement of all stakeholders in the transformation journey to climate resilience. To face this challenge, the platform proposed by FARCLIMATE has been conceived as a Transformation Hub, user-centred, with a social innovation approach and a co-creative design process to frame the contents and communicate the solutions adequately to different users.

2.2.2. Steps in the process of creating the FARCLIMATE Transformation Hub

The **FARCLIMATE Transformation Hub** will be developed within the framework of WP7, based on a co-design process involving various stakeholders and following a user-centred approach, adhering to a co-creation scheme consisting of four main steps (Figure 1):

1. **User-led innovation**: through workshops, surveys and interviews, the main needs will be identified.
2. **Platform-design proposal**: following the explained communication approach, a design proposal will be developed for further codesign
3. **Platform development**: all technical steps to build the platform.
4. **User experience assessment**: to test the functionality of the platform under the considered objectives. Needed changes in the design or in the technical part will be accomplished to achieve all set objectives.

2.2.3. Purpose and objectives of Task T.7.1. User research and content strategy development

This report provides the context within which the approach of WP7 of the FARCLIMATE project is framed, specifically focusing on the Transformation Hub. It subsequently directs attention to the description of the activities carried out in **Task T.7.1**: User research and content strategy development (step 1 of Figure 1), which has been executed during the period from October 2023 to September 2024.

Alongside documentary research to characterise the climate adaptation ecosystem, the first phase of user research addressed two key aspects for defining the content strategy:

- The analysis of how the different **user archetypes interact** with and **experience** the main adaptation platforms.
- The analysis of **users' perceptions** of the **relevance** of the case study content and its ability to assist users in making decisions.

The results of this phase, whose methodology and development are presented in sections 3 to 7, have been systematised into the key findings from experiential insights reflected in section 8, ultimately outlining the platform content strategy in section 9.

3. Methodological approach

The methodological approach of Task T.7.1 has been structured into four complementary actions, which are described in detail in sections 4 to 7 of this document:

- Documentary research and review of existing platforms.
- Initial exploration with potential users.
- Definition of target audience and scale.
- Interviews with potential users, who represent the primary user archetypes.

4. Documentary research and review of existing platforms

As a starting point for formulating the content strategy of the platform, it is necessary to conduct a review of the state of the art and identify relevant references (entities, projects, platforms, etc.) in the field of climate adaptation. The academic documentary research, conducted using well-known scientific databases such as Web of Science, Scopus, and ScienceDirect, was complemented by a thorough review of documentation, reports, and evaluations related to EU policies, as well as the mapping of ongoing projects, platforms, and initiatives, with particular attention paid to the content curated by the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, which has been included in the EU Mission Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt). **Annex 1** presents a selection of the projects and platforms considered of greatest interest for the goals and scope of FARCLIMATE.

5. Initial exploration with potential users

The initial exploration with potential users was conducted by taking advantage of the face-to-face activities carried out in the first months of the FARCLIMATE project: the Kick-off Meeting (KoM) and the training directed at the representatives of the project case studies.

Exploratory Exercise – KoM

The complementarity of the profiles achieved in FARCLIMATE creates a unique consortium to conduct cutting-edge research and outreach. With a strong emphasis on academic, industrial, and governmental collaborations, FARCLIMATE integrates 14 partners from diverse stakeholder profiles, providing an excellent foundation for the user research necessary for an efficient and effective design of the Transformation Hub. Leveraging the meeting space generated by the FARCLIMATE Kick-off Meeting, which took place in the city of Vigo, Spain, from October 18–19, 2023, a preliminary exploratory exercise was conducted to validate the 'what' and the 'how' of the Transformation Hub and to initiate a collective discussion about the potential users to prioritise for the development of the platform. After a brief introduction to the objectives of WP7 and the steps for developing the Transformation Hub, all participants were invited to reflect on the Hub's target audience, which should be involved in the co-design process, and to identify the most appropriate channels for establishing contact and interaction with the various user archetypes. Additionally, a discussion was opened on which references (entities, projects, initiatives) are considered most relevant in the context of the FARCLIMATE Project. Participants' responses were collected in post-it format (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Post-it notes capturing insights from the exploratory exercise during the FARCLIMATE KoM. Left: users of the Transformation

participation was that the representative joining the event should be external to the consortium and should be familiar with the bottom-up activities of the case study, possessing a deep understanding of its vision, mission, stakeholders, challenges, strengths, business model, and more. This representative was expected to provide as many details as possible about the case study and its day-to-day activities.

Following the sessions on Introduction to Living Labs in case studies, the training focused on stakeholder engagement through two sessions led by INV, during which two practical exercises were presented, concentrating on the initial phase of Living Lab setup:

Exercise 1: Landing in the Journey

In this exercise, participants were invited to reflect on their current position in the Living Lab journey. The focus was on mapping stakeholders and challenges.

Guiding Questions:

- **Stakeholders:** Participants were asked whether the stakeholders had been mapped, the level of accuracy of this mapping, and who was responsible for it. They also considered if at least some of the stakeholders were actively engaged in the process.
- **Challenges:** Participants reflected on whether the challenges that the Living Lab would address had been identified and mapped. They discussed who defined and selected these challenges to ensure a clear focus for the lab's objectives.

Exercise 2: Initial Setup Plan

The second exercise centred around designing an initial setup plan for the Living Lab. Participants outlined key components, including:

- **Actions:** They defined specific objectives, established a timeline, identified participants, and allocated resources needed for the setup.
- **Call to Action:** Participants were prompted to consider what actions they would take following the workshop, encouraging them to think about the next steps in their Living Lab journey.

Figure 5. Working groups in the training exercises designed for the FARCLIMATE case studies.

These exercises aimed to foster critical thinking and practical planning, ensuring participants could effectively navigate the initial phases of their Living Lab projects. The discussions held during the exercises facilitated a deeper understanding of the needs and priorities of the case studies, providing valuable insights for further elaboration and integration into the definition of the strategic design framework for the Transformation Hub.

6. Definition of target audience and scale

Building on the initial exploration, the original approach was refined, with a more precise focus on the target audience and scale of intervention. This was followed by a deeper investigation into the needs and priorities of potential users through interviews. The established guidelines are presented below:

Focused on territory-led processes (connected to the idea of “just and inclusive transition,” as it involves local actors and is fair to the diversity of stakeholders involved). Therefore, it targets organised civil society actors at the local/regional level, which we consider to be organised in three domains: public institutions, private economic agents, and formal and informal community organizations. Certain organisations may sometimes encompass functions across multiple spheres (for example, a fishers' guild operates at the intersection of the economic and community spheres).

Spatial scale. In accordance with the focus on territory-led processes, the spatial scale should move between local and regional. There may not be a single appropriate scale for the climate adaptation processes covered in FARCLIMATE, as this will depend on the nature of the problems. We find it promising to explore the bioregional scale, where ecological, economic (when economic activities heavily depend on ecosystems), and governance units converge.

Primary users of the Hub, our primary target audience: those responsible at local and regional levels for public institutions, economic activities, or community organisations (representatives of civil society).

Additionally, the Hub will have secondary users. It is not designed with these archetypes as a priority, but we are aware that they will be users, and we must consider their interests. Among these secondary users are citizens (“unorganised”) and technical and political representatives of public institutions at regional, state, or European levels.

What role do scientists play? Depending on the type of science and knowledge they generate, they may be more “at the service” of public policies (and therefore would be secondary users) or be part of alliances and projects that address climate adaptation by developing solutions from the territory (and thus would be primary users collaborating with public, economic, or community organisations).

Why do we select **local leaders** as **priority** users?

- Need for territory-led processes.
- Focus on final solutions rather than public policies (which, if designed, would be at larger spatial scales).
- “Unorganised” citizens, with individual and uncoordinated actions (if there is coordination, there are already organisational forms, whether formal or informal), have limited capacity to generate an impact in their territory.

The Hub consists of a knowledge base and a series of interfaces and tools that allow for the effective use of that knowledge according to the needs and interests of the user. In this sense, it is essential to start from the functions that we believe knowledge use should have in order to promote effective climate adaptation processes. We can consider **three fundamental functions of the Hub:**

- Awareness-raising about issues that may be impacting that territory, its socio-ecological resilience, and its economic activities.
- Inspiration to promote climate adaptation initiatives based on notable experiences from other territories that serve as references due to similarities in the types of challenges, socio-economic contexts, or the nature of actions and leadership exercised.
- Transfer and adaptation of solutions.

In summary, the Transformation Hub is not a platform for creating public policy but rather for intervening in real-world situations. We view public policy as a tool to facilitate the implementation of solutions, whereas most climate knowledge platforms are designed for policy purposes and therefore lack utility for other stakeholders -those seeking practical, specific solutions and applications. This focus has significant implications for the curation of relevant and meaningful knowledge that enables effective use, the way narratives are developed from this knowledge, and the use of clear, accessible language for primary users.

7. Interviews with user archetypes

7.1 Approach and script for semi-structured interviews

Selection of participants for interviews

The individuals selected for interviews represented user archetypes corresponding to the primary users defined for the Transformation Hub. Specifically, a total of eight people (five women, three men) were interviewed, representing regional public institutions (1), organisations working with economic sectors (4), and community and civil society organisations (3).

Format of interviews

The interviews were semi-structured, lasting approximately 45 to 60 minutes, and followed an open conversational format. A flexible script (not shared beforehand) was used by the interviewers to guide the discussion. Each interview was conducted by two people: one acting as the primary interviewer, leading the dialogue, and the other taking notes and contributing occasionally.

At the start of each interview, confidentiality was emphasised, with an assurance that no ideas or opinions would be attributed to specific individuals (though in some cases, they might be associated with a functional profile within the organisation). To reinforce a trusting environment, no recordings were made, and notes were taken by the interviewers during the interview.

Guide to topics for interviews

Before beginning the process, a script was prepared to guide the interviewers, though with a high degree of flexibility. As such, topics were introduced based on the interviewee's relevant experiences and opinions, and space was provided to discuss any other topics they considered important.

The interview script was structured into six sections, each with prompt questions established:

0. Introduction, stating the:

- **Interview conditions:** Only for internal and confidential use. No recordings. Notes will be taken.
- **Objective of the Interview:** To gather perspectives and experiences from representatives of primary users, which will be valuable in designing a truly effective Transformation Hub.

1. Familiarity with the climate adaptation concept:

- To what extent are you and your work environment familiar with the concept of 'climate adaptation,' and how important is it considered in the work you do?

2. Practices of information search for climate adaptation:

- Have you needed to seek information on climate adaptation (solutions to problems caused by climate change applicable to your activity/area)? If so, how did you go about it?

3. Knowledge platforms of relevance:

- Is there any knowledge platform (even if not related to climate change/adaptation) that you use in your work and find helpful? What do you find interesting about it (content, presentation formats, ease of use, etc.)?

4. Climate knowledge platforms:

- Are you aware of any knowledge platforms related to climate change/adaptation?

5. User Exploration of Climate-ADAPT:

- We will show you the Climate-ADAPT platform (<https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en>) and ask you to navigate and explore it to evaluate your perceptions.

6. Information for the Transformation Hub.

- What information and functionalities would you like to find in the Transformation Hub?

7.2 Analysis of the Interviews

A qualitative analysis of the interviews was performed including first the documentation and codification of insights of individual interviews and followed by the thematic mapping and integration of the different interviews to generate a summary covering the main insights related to the topics addressed in the interviews.

The methodological sequence is briefly summarised below:

A. Initial documentation of the interviews

The first coding of each interview and selection of relevant information is conducted in real-time during the interview while taking notes. In each interview, the notes take the form of a series of items (phrases and paragraphs summarising the ideas and narratives communicated by the interviewee) organised chronologically. These items may represent opinions, experiences, relevant facts and data or identified problems and needs related to the scope of the interview.

These notes were subsequently digitised shortly after the interview to avoid losing contextual information. The contents were digitised in Miro, with the coded items from each of the six interview questions organised into thematic categories.

B. Thematic mapping of interview content

Through mind maps, the findings were organised for each of the six main initial questions, establishing thematic groupings that include all individual insights (mind maps generated from the analysis of user interviews are compiled in **Annex 2**). Each interviewee contributes a unique universe of differentiated experience and observation, together forming a broad and diverse picture of different perspectives and experiences. All are experts in their fields, and their observations, ideas, and concerns are relevant and should be considered in this phase of the project.

Naturally, this picture includes grey areas, gaps, and occasional discrepancies or differing viewpoints. The aim of this exercise is not to generate a quantitative or statistical overview but rather to provide a coherent and structured image that captures the diversity of experiences and perspectives.

To achieve this, the different mapped findings for each question were integrated into a narrative based on a series of key ideas or themes. In some cases, several similar findings were condensed into a single item, while in others, items unique to a group of interviewees were included. Additionally, certain discrepancies between ideas may be present, reflecting the coexistence of diverse perspectives within the interviewed group.

C. Summary identifying the most critical/strategic insights

From the thematic mapping of findings (the main result of the analysis), summaries have been created by theme to highlight the aspects considered most relevant and strategic. These summaries are presented in the following section of this document.

8. Key findings from experience insights

Below are the main results obtained from the interviews in terms of the **perspective** of the potential primary users about their understanding of the **impact** and **urgency** of climate adaptation and their **knowledge** about available digital resources and their utility.

Information obtained from interviews regarding **user needs** for knowledge and guidance to implement effective adaptation solutions, as well as insights into information architecture and user experience in digital platforms that could enhance the utility of the future Hub, forms the foundation on which the **content strategy** proposal for the platform, presented in Section 9.2, has been developed.

8.1 Climate adaptation concept and practices of information search

Awareness about the climate adaptation concept

General **citizens** (without specific economic activities impacted directly by climate change) are not aware of the concept of climate adaptation. However, **professionals and business owners** in sectors dependent on the natural environment are already suffering the impact of climate change and have a high level of awareness, especially those engaged in ecological

management, which heightens their sensitivity to these issues. Examples of sectors and professionals acutely affected by and aware of climate impacts include farmers, who face challenges such as crop changes and new pests and diseases; winegrowers, adapting to changes in grape varieties and shifting cultivation to higher altitudes; beekeepers, impacted by shifts in flowering periods; forestry professionals managing increased fire risks and pest pressures; and cattle raisers, contending with changing pasture conditions and water availability.

Public institutions and **community organisations** at the local and regional levels generally have a high degree of climate awareness and have internalised the impacts of climate change, as they are directly affected in their activities and priorities. For example, in Mediterranean forestry, where models indicate severe climate impacts, all management decisions now must consider factors like species selection for reforestation or forest density, which are heavily influenced by climate-dependent environmental factors.

Characteristics of the information available about climate change and adaptation

Users perceive that climate information is generally focused on long-term predictions and often presents a 'highly catastrophic vision.' In contrast, many individuals and organisations recognise the **relevance** of the issue but feel it lacks short-term urgency. They face **difficulties** in finding **practical solutions** to their challenges, highlighting the need for more tailored adaptation strategies relevant to specific sectors and territories. It's important to note that people in organisations considered primary users are not experts but are generally interested in deepening their understanding of the topic.

Practices of information search for climate adaptation

Searching for information should be a **learning process** that enables organisations to build their own **knowledge** base. However, it is typically not a primary activity, and searches are often superficial. Recently, some organisations have begun to pay more attention due to the increasing relevance of climate-related issues. Many organisations remain reactive, addressing urgent problems as they arise ('putting out fires') and dealing with significant bureaucratic constraints, both of which limit their capacity to conduct strategic information searches.

In general, there are no established processes or practices for information searching, which often depends on the initiative of individuals within the organisation (their interests, skills, and background). There is also a widespread sense that adequate **solutions from science are not effectively transferred**.

Channels to access relevant information about climate adaptation

People and organisations use a variety of channels and tools to search, access and understand relevant information for their interest and work:

- **Internet**, employing diverse approaches, including general internet searches via search engines (Google being the most cited), consulting research papers, leveraging contact networks, conducting deep dives on specific websites, and accessing academic publications.
- **Allies and networks**. Collaboration with organisations and networks provides access to valuable knowledge they generate and share through various channels, including formal and periodic updates (e.g., newsletters), closed discussion forums within alliances of

multiple institutions, events, project participation, and direct contact with experts, both internal and external to the organisation.

- **Public administration.** While public administration tends to be slow, it possesses some of the most powerful information collection systems, which are useful for analysing historical trends. However, interviews highlighted additional limitations to the utility of public administrations, such as restricted horizontal communication among territorial entities—even within the same public administration—and the very limited transfer of knowledge from research centres to public management institutions and other organisations.

Some examples of networks and platforms cited as relevant by interviewees:

- IUCN is identified in various interviews as a key source of information.
- Project PescaConCiencia in Spain, involving collaboration among several Local Action Groups (LAGs).
- LAG fund collaborative projects between fishers' guilds and universities.
- At a regional level, the Mesa Social del Agua de Andalucía: <https://redandaluzaagua.org/msa/>.
- "Congreso Forestal" in Spain is their main dissemination channel for forestry.

The importance of local (experiential) knowledge

Most informants recognise the value of local knowledge, but in only a few cases are they able to access and organise it in a formal and structured manner. For example, gathering local knowledge from forestry agents can help detect emerging trends and facilitate early decision-making.

8.2 User exploration of knowledge platforms

Knowledge platforms of relevance

Most individuals are not aware of relevant platforms or provide examples while noting that these platforms have significant limitations. The following platforms were identified as references that interviewees consider of interest:

- Forestry Portal of Castilla y León (designed and developed by CESEFOR): <https://pfcyl.es/>.
- eBird, citizen science for ornithology. Combines app, coordinators (scientific experts), citizens and university project. <https://ebird.org/home>.
- Green Growth Generation website: <https://greengrowthgeneration.com/>.
- REEDUCAMAR - Network and inventory of marine education resources in Spain: <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/ceneam/recursos/mini-portales-tematicos/reeducamar.html>.
- UE FAMENET - Fisheries and Aquaculture Monitoring, Evaluation and Local Support Network: https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/funding/famenet_en.
- Scopus, as example of database for research publications. <https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus>
- Copernicus, the EU Climate platform. <https://climate.copernicus.eu/>.

Climate knowledge platforms

In general, interviewees did not identify any specific platforms of interest; however, they commented on the existence of several interesting sites, albeit highly specialised.

The following are the platforms identified:

- US Forest Service. Climate (includes a section about Climate Change). <https://www.fs.usda.gov/science-technology/climate-change>.
- CESEFOR website. <https://www.cesefor.com/es>.
- Climate content of the World Economic Forum (WEF). <https://www.weforum.org/>.

User exploration of Climate-ADAPT

Most interviewees were not aware of the platform or had never used it, but during the exploration conducted in the interview, many discovered that the platform contains relevant information. For some users, the concept of climate change is perceived as too broad and generic (and has become overused), which does not encourage them to see the information as useful for their specific needs.

The first impression of the Climate-ADAPT platform is that it feels “cold” and technical, primarily oriented towards specialists. Additionally, language poses a significant barrier; some users, during their initial contact, did not notice the option to select a language. Furthermore, part of the site is only available in English.

Most of the content on the platform has a broad focus on **large scale / public policy**, while the interviewees expressed greater interest in specific sectoral and territorial solutions. Many interviewees focused on and positively valued the case study sheets, appreciating that they appear to be updated and help users determine their interest in further exploration. However, case studies related to fisheries are very limited; for instance, there are no case studies on seaweed. It would be beneficial if each piece of content provided access to more detailed information (such as databases, other sites, and research papers). The platform includes many generic resources (such as reports) but offers few specific contents, which could be the most valuable

Regarding the **architecture** of the **information** and **navigation experience**:

- There is no guide or search tool to topics of interest for the user and scrolling down through the home it seems that contents are repeated.
- "Case studies" navigation would benefit from the use of categories and keywords (now you need many clicks to arrive at the case studies of interest). They focus on case studies but don't find keywords (in the landing of the section) to access specific information.
- The criteria for ordering search results are unclear.
- It has been noted that some links are dead, particularly those directing to original projects that are no longer active.
- In general, the platform uses long text formats, but the content is well-structured, allowing for agile and focused reading (with summaries and main topics). Some users don't mind the length of the text, while others find it unattractive due to the lack of visual components (primarily images).
- In general, the platform uses too long format texts but with good structure allowing an agile and focused reading (with summaries, main topics ...). Some users don't mind that

there is a lot of text, but others don't find it attractive because of the lack of visual components (mostly images)

- The "Sectors" section effectively uses icons, but the content appears repetitive when scrolling down.

9. Platform content strategy

The content strategy is developed based on the strategic guidelines and key functionalities of the Transformation Hub identified through the user research process.

9.1 Strategic framework

Design principles for the Transformation Hub

The process of research, ideation, prototyping and validation of the Transformation Hub will be based in the following design principles:

User-centred and co-design. All the phases of the process will involve users to ensure that the Hub is genuinely user-centric in the sense of the functionalities and experience. Users will not only be information providers, and they will participate actively in the conceptualization, design and validation of the different elements of the Hub. Primary and secondary users will be defined, and priority will be given to the primary users to fill the gaps detected with the present climate adaptation platforms.

Agile. Successive cycles of validation with increasing levels of complexity and technological development to assure that the "final product" fits with the needs of the users and have the capacity of pivoting along the process.

Interoperability and preference for open source solutions. Technological decisions will prioritise tools and standards that maximise the ability to connect and interact with other projects and knowledge bases, facilitating the expansion and replication of the developed tools across different contexts.

A collective action ladder

The Transformation Hub serves as a knowledge platform, conceived as a collective action ladder (Figure 6) with the following generic functions:

- A repository of content.
- Basic tools for access, consultation, and retrieval.
- Fundamental features for user interaction, dialogue, project design, and decision-making.

As a starting point for formulating the content strategy of the platform, the review of the state of the art conducted and the relevant references identified (entities, projects, platforms, etc.) in the field of climate adaptation must be systematised to generate a dataset that will be used as input for **Task T7.3 - Platform Development**, as well as for the visualisation in **Task T6.5 - Connected Action for EU Adaptation**. The dataset will provide a characterization of the climate change adaptation ecosystem that will be useful for all stakeholders interested in engaging with this field. The data will be open access and will adhere to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) requirements. The dataset will incorporate three types of records:

1) Entity: a relevant agent involved in research-action processes in climate adaptation; 2) Product: encoded knowledge that provides an effective solution for climate change adaptation in a specific context (e.g., a platform); 3) Process: an activity executed within a specific period in the field of climate adaptation (e.g., a European-funded project).

Figure 6. Conceptual framework of the collective action ladder.

Gleaning lessons from Climate-ADAPT to guide the content strategy

The content strategy is based on the findings from the interviews and the document review, allowing us to complement our understanding of user needs with an analysis of the weaknesses of existing platforms and tools. Given its relevance to the European context, special attention has been paid to analysing the Climate-ADAPT platform.

Climate-ADAPT was evaluated in 2018 (EEA, 2018) and has been regularly updated to meet new knowledge needs and policy requirements, most recently to support the priorities of the EU's Adaptation Strategy (EC, 2021) and the tasks outlined in the European Climate Law. Another evaluation is currently underway, which will provide insights into how to further improve Climate-ADAPT to address the new knowledge needs of the upcoming EU policy term. The briefing titled "Preparing Society for Climate Risks in Europe: Lessons and Inspiration from Climate-ADAPT Case Studies," published by the EEA in June 2024, aims to inspire further adaptation actions across Europe by presenting Climate-ADAPT case studies as a pool of practical examples of implemented adaptation measures. These case studies are a key means of supporting and enhancing the implementation of adaptation policies and planning at all governance levels across Europe. It is not yet possible to effectively determine the full impact of the case studies, including how many actions they have inspired and in which instances they have been scaled up for broader application. However, feedback from the 2018 Climate-ADAPT evaluation indicates that the case studies were used as illustrative examples for strategic

adaptation planning, research-oriented purposes, and stakeholder dialogues. More recent feedback from conferences at the EU, national, and local levels shows continued interest in the case studies. Moreover, the case studies section is the second most visited feature on Climate-ADAPT, averaging 8,100 page views per month in 2023.

Despite all the efforts made, an analysis by sector (Figure 7) reveals a very uneven representation. Based on increased adaptation actions under EU initiatives and funding, and in alignment with the priorities of the EU adaptation strategy and national-level actions, the water management, disaster risk reduction, and urban sectors demonstrate the largest share of Climate-ADAPT case studies. In contrast, the forestry sector, which necessitates a long-term perspective and ongoing adjustments rather than a single-year investment, is represented by a relatively lower number of case studies. Notably, while the agriculture and marine and fisheries sectors are critical to EU climate resilience, their representation in case studies remains limited. These sectors face significant climate risks and require innovative adaptation strategies to ensure sustainability and productivity in the face of changing environmental conditions. Providing case studies in the three sectors that FARCLIMATE focuses on, which are underrepresented in Climate-ADAPT, is a priority action area in the content strategy of the Transformation Hub.

Figure 7. Climate-ADAPT case studies per policy sector, structured according to the Climate-ADAPT sector classification. Source: EEA (2024).

9.2 Key features and content

Using the insights gathered from interviews with potential primary users, documentary analysis, and observations from various activities conducted within the FARCLIMATE project, a preliminary proposal for the content strategy, information architecture, and usability of the Transformation Hub is presented below

1. General functionalities and experience

The Hub should provide a systematic overview of the climate adaptation challenge within a sectoral and territorial context. The focus should be on building the capacity of users and their organisations to anticipate problems and identify potential solutions. In other words, the Hub

could serve as a 'place' for users to stay informed about climate change, where challenges and existing solutions specific to their sector are communicated.

Content curation and narratives should be aligned and tailored to the characteristics of the user archetypes, acknowledging their diversity. In this regard, including arguments and explanations about the relevance of the content is essential for generating user interest and engagement.

The initial interaction (first "touch") with the Hub is crucial and should emphasise why the topic is relevant and how the Hub can be useful. Additionally, it should support multiple languages, allowing users to search by language, as resources available only in English pose a barrier for some users, particularly those who are primary users of the Hub.

2. Main contents identified as valuable

- Good practices including examples of both successful and unsuccessful case studies, in terms of projects and implementations. It is essential to avoid biases associated with only selecting "positive results" and to include learnings from "negative results and experiences".
- Toolkits / toolboxes (canvas, roadmaps, ...).
- Graphical abstracts or summaries presented in video or infographic formats.
- Effective access to the cited resources (e.g., option to download papers).
- Contact info for the responsible of case studies.
- People of reference in different topics.
- Catalogues of organisations and companies with potential solutions and tools.
- Local knowledge (see point 4).

3. How to structure the information and guide search and navigation

- Organise content by geographical areas and economic sectors.
- Ensure intuitive and efficient access to themes and topics.
- Incorporate keywords to facilitate search.
- Use maps to display case studies and other resources.

4. How to include and manage local (experiential) knowledge

Local knowledge could be beneficial in two main aspects:

- Understanding environmental conditions and trends.
- Conducting "quasi-experiments" through small interventions by users in response to problems arising from climate change.

Traditionally, digital literacy has been a barrier to local user participation. However, new generations of users have a better capacity to connect local knowledge with technical and digital skills. The design of the Hub should address the following challenges related to incorporating local knowledge:

- How to standardise and validate local knowledge for inclusion in the system.
- Addressing the nature of individual incentives for providing information.
- Ensuring that commercial interests do not compromise the reliability of the information.
- Providing tutorials to facilitate the work of local informants.

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Annex 1. List of relevant projects identified in the field of climate adaptation

Featured projects

Regions for climate change resilience through Innovation, Science and Technology -RESIST project

<https://resist-project.eu/>

Regions4Climate project -R4C project

<https://regions4climate.eu/>

Dynamic information management approach for the implementation of climate resilient adaptation packages in European regions- IMPETUS project

<https://climate-impetus.eu/>

A Gathering place to co-design and co-create Adaptation – AGORA project

<https://adaptationagora.eu/>

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation packages – TransformAr project

<https://transformar.eu/>

Climate resilient regions through systemic solutions and innovations – ARSINOE project

<https://arsinoe-project.eu/>

Climate-Resilient Development Pathways in Metropolitan Regions of Europe – CARMINE project

<https://www.carmine-project.eu/>

Accelerating transformative climate adaptation for higher resilience in European mountain regions – MountResilience project

<https://mountresilience.eu/#home>

Multi-hazard Infrastructure Risk Assessment for Climate Adaptation – MIRACA project

<https://miraca-project.eu/>

Resilience Strategies for Regions – REGILIENCE project

<https://regilience.eu/>

Nature Based Solutions for Atlantic Regional Climate Resilience – NBRACER project

<https://nbracer.eu/>

Accelerating and mainstreaming transformative NATure-bAsed solutions to enhance resilience to climate change for diverse bio-geographical European regions – NATALIE project

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101112859>

User driven climate applications empowering regional resilience – ClimEmpower project

<https://climempower.eu/about/>

CLIMAtE change citizens engagement toolbox for dealing with Societal resilience – CLIMAS project

<https://www.climas-project.eu/>

Featured platforms

Climate-ADAPT

<https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en>

CAP

<https://climateadaptationplatform.com/>

A-PLAT

<https://adaptation-platform.nies.go.jp/en/index.html>

Featured initiatives

Climate Adaptation & Mitigation Impact Area Platform – CGIAR

<https://www.cgiar.org/research/cgiar-portfolio/climate-adaptation-mitigation/platform/>

Canada's Climate Change Adaptation Platform

<https://natural-resources.canada.ca/climate-change/canadas-climate-change-adaptation-platform/10027>

UNFCCC's Adaptation Exchange

<https://unfccc.int/news/join-the-adaptation-exchange>

Annex 2. Mind maps analysing user archetype interview content

2.1. Familiarity with the climate adaptation concept

2.2. Practices of information search for climate adaptation

Practices of information search for climate adaptation

2.3. Knowledge platforms of relevance

Knowledge platforms of relevance

General perspective

Most of the people are not aware of relevant platforms or provide some examples commenting that they have serious limitations

Platforms identified

"Portal Forestal de Castilla y León" (depending of CESEFOR):
<https://pfcyl.es/>

eBird, citizen science for ornithology. Combines app, coordinators (scientific experts), citizens and university project.
<https://ebird.org/home>

Green Growth Generation website
<https://greengrowthgeneration.com/>

REEDUCAMAR, la red e inventario de recursos de educación marina de España:
<https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/ceneam/recursos/mini-portales-tematicos/reeducamar.html>

UE FAMENET (Fisheries and Aquaculture Monitoring, Evaluation and Local Support Network):
https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/funding/famenet_en

Scopus, as example of database for research publications
<https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus>

Copernicus, the EU Climate platform
<https://climate.copernicus.eu/>

Climate knowledge platforms

General perspective

In general, interviewees did not identify any platform of interest

However commented about the existence of several interesting sites but in general highly specific

US Forest Service. Climate (includes a section about Climate Change):
<https://www.fs.usda.gov/science-technology/climate-change>

Platforms identified

Website CESEFOR:
<https://www.cesefor.com/es>

Climate content of the World Economic Forum (WEF):
<https://www.weforum.org/>

2.4. User exploration of Climate-ADAPT

User exploration of CLIMATE ADAPT

2.5. Information for the Transformation Hub

